

Commercial and regulatory frameworks for postbiotics: non-viable microbial agents conferring a beneficial physiological effect

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Abstract

The current postbiotic commercial landscape is fragmented and lacks standardization. This manuscript delves into the realm of postbiotics, defined here as non-viable microbial ingredients that confer beneficial physiological effects when administered through food and dietary supplements, exploring their categorization and nomenclature within the commercial and regulatory frameworks. The International Probiotic Association (IPA) coordinated structured meetings and informal discussions, integrating feedback from its members, regulatory agencies, and global stakeholders to analyze technical and manufacturing processes, safety considerations, and regulatory implications, leading to a comprehensive framework for standardizing bioactive ingredients. This process refined a roadmap that balances scientific rigor and commercial relevance. A decision tree is introduced to classify postbiotics into four distinct subcategories, translating decades of divergent academic research into practical, technical, and commercial considerations. Additionally, the manuscript highlights the critical need for clear guidelines and standards to ensure ingredient safety, quality, and efficacy. By drawing on existing scientific knowledge from the probiotic field and identifying technical gaps, the manuscript advocates for the harmonization of criteria and nomenclature to foster communication and consistency among stakeholders. As interest in postbiotics grows across industries, establishing a robust commercial and regulatory framework is essential to foster innovation, guide scientific communication, and ensure consumer protection in this emerging category.

Keywords: postbiotics, paraprobiotics, metabiotics, probiotics, ghostbiotics, non-viable microbial bioactives, regulatory frameworks.

1. Introduction

The focus in global biotic commercial markets is increasingly expanding from living organisms to their non-viable components, parts, or metabolites, reflecting the growing perception that ‘non-viable microbial biotics are the next significant innovation after probiotics’. This trend is driven by various factors. Some academic groups argue that commercial restrictions on applications and translocation risks are primary reasons for exploring non-viable microbes beyond probiotics ¹. In contrast, others reference the risk of horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes ², or challenges in viability controls within probiotic products ^{3,4}. But whilst this movement is undoubtedly here to stay, confusion persists regarding its categorization and nomenclature.

Postbiotics, paraprobiotics, ghost probiotics, metabiotics, and all other terms pertaining to non-viable ‘biotics’ have been proposed to indicate non-living microorganisms that exert physiological effects. Among these, the term ‘postbiotics’, which was originally introduced in the literature in 2009 by Johannsen and Prescott ⁵ and then formally defined in 2012 and 2013 by Rescigno et al. ^{6,7}, has become popular ⁸, though its meaning is still under academic debate ⁹. Currently, there is an illusion of consensus surrounding the meaning and definition of the term “postbiotic” that is worthy of historical context. In 2021, an academic definition of postbiotics was published that catapulted the term “postbiotic” into popularity in industry: *“a preparation of inanimate microorganisms and/or their components that confers health benefit on the host”* ⁸. However, the term “postbiotic” was originally proposed approximately ten years earlier ⁵⁻⁷ and adopted in hundreds of scientific publications with a profoundly different meaning, *i.e.*, to indicate *“any substance released by or produced through the metabolic activity of the microorganism, which exerts a beneficial effect on the host”* ¹⁰. Thus, the lack of academic consensus surrounding the 2021 definition by Salminen and co-workers may stem from a significant divergence from the original concept of postbiotic proposed in 2009. This original definition characterized postbiotics as the factors released from microbes as opposed to postbiotics being the intact or broken microbial cells themselves, which were initially referred to as paraprobiotics (*“non-viable microbial cells (intact or broken) or crude cell extracts (i.e., with complex chemical composition), which, when administered (orally or topically) in adequate amounts, confer a benefit on the human or animal consumer”*; ¹¹). This distinction was highlighted in a letter to the editor authored by a large group of academic experts ⁹. Furthermore, two additional academic definitions of “postbiotics” were proposed

and subsequently published, returning to the concepts underlying the original definition ^{12,13}. Thus, to date, there is still no academic, commercial, regulatory, or otherwise stakeholder consensus as to what constitutes any of the introduced terms in Table 1 or concepts relating to non-viable microbial agents that confer a physiological effect ⁹.

Other terms have been used to describe both non-viable microbes and their derivatives, including tyndallized or heat-killed. In 2013 and 2016, the term “metabiotic” was also proposed to be defined as, “*structural components of probiotic microorganisms and/or their metabolites and/or signaling molecules with a determined chemical structure that can optimize host-specific physiological functions, regulatory, metabolic and/or behavior reactions connected with the activity of host indigenous microbiota*” ^{14,15}. It should also be noted that new terms are being used in marketing to describe ingredients and oftentimes finished products (e.g., eubiotic, ferment essence, and so on).

We will not enter the discussion about which word or term of the previously published is the most appropriate. Instead, **considering the entire history of the terms and category and the current commercial situation, we will use the term ‘postbiotic’ as the umbrella name for the entire category, in other words, all concepts outlined in Table 1.**

Besides the divergent terminology and lack of consensus, all proposed academic definitions in Table 1 fail to address various technical, manufacturing, and regulatory considerations, such as quality standards for the starting materials, standardization throughout various manufacturing phases, enumeration/quantification of the bioactive entities, and label requirements for consumers. Furthermore, if researchers (un)knowingly limit themselves to one term and its associated body of literature, this may have impact on critical investigations in safety, dosing, mechanisms of action, compatibilities with other ingredients, and so on. Additionally, safety considerations remain a critical and ongoing topic of discussion within regulatory circles. Because of the risk associated with implying pseudo-scientific words that are not consensually or legally defined, there is a risk of regulatory restrictions on claims, something that is very familiar within the European probiotic field. Some of the unaddressed or unanswered questions regarding postbiotics are outlined below:

- Should the progenitor strain (i.e., the live microbial strain from which the postbiotic is derived) be probiotic or not (i.e., must it have beneficial physiological effects)?

- Can the safety of a postbiotic be reliably inferred from the history of safe consumption of a progenitor strain?
- What manufacturing and regulatory standards should be implemented to ensure the safety and quality of a postbiotic?
- What are the acceptable safety requirements for the progenitor strain from a regulatory perspective?
- How to differentiate between metabolites, lysates, cellular fragments, and components of the culture medium?
- What distinguishes an inactivated or non-viable microorganism from a one in a state of metabolic dormancy or 'viable but not culturable' state?
- What entities should be excluded from the categories of postbiotics (*e.g.*, viruses and phages, antibiotics, vaccines, etc.)?
- Should synthetically produced, yet nature-identical, components be classified as postbiotics?
- What industrial manufacturing standards and quality control techniques should be reasonably applied?
- What is the acceptable upper limit of viable cells within postbiotic preparations?

Appropriate market translation of the aforementioned neglected commercial considerations for postbiotics should be built upon tightly controlled manufacturing processes, use of suitable technical methodologies, proper process validation and quality standards, and pre- and post-market surveillance to ensure safe and efficacious ingredients for products.

This paper proposes a set of criteria to be considered from both commercial and regulatory perspectives when addressing **postbiotic ingredients, including microbial bioactive compounds, metabolic byproducts, cell components, and non-viable microorganisms**. To this end, we leveraged existing technical and scientific knowledge alongside commercial expertise gained from decades of experience with probiotics. Over approximately two years, under the patronage of the International Probiotic Association (IPA), we conducted structured meetings and informal discussions, integrating feedback from members, regulatory agencies, and global stakeholders (scientists, regulators, manufacturers, and marketers). This process involved analyzing technical and manufacturing processes, safety considerations, and regulatory implications, leading to a refined roadmap that balances scientific rigor

and commercial relevance. Ultimately, we propose a comprehensive framework for standardizing these bioactive ingredients.

2. Scope of application

To bring any agent conferring a beneficial physiological effect to the market, the intended use within the scope of application guides the regulatory framework of the final ingredient or product. Postbiotic foods and dietary supplements are generally intended for healthy populations, and as such are not meant to treat, cure, or prevent disease. Although certain postbiotic ingredients and products could fall under drug regulations, **this manuscript focuses exclusively on those intended for human applications within foods and dietary supplements.**

Similar considerations can be made regarding feeds, cosmetics, etc.

3. Regulatory considerations

Regulatory authorities are primarily responsible for ensuring that anything within their purview is safe, efficacious (where relevant), and fit for its intended purpose. They also influence and control how this information is communicated to consumers, depending on the type of market entry (*e.g.*, post-policing versus pre-approval). This includes an oversight of ingredient nomenclature, ensuring that in a market where consumers choose to purchase and consume products without professional guidance, they can make informed decisions. Full disclosure of a product's contents and ingredients on the finished product label is essential to facilitate transparency and consumer trust.

Government authorities around the world are exploring the regulation of the postbiotic category, but there are no official published guidelines or regulations for postbiotics as food/dietary supplements or foods to date. The current situation for postbiotics globally varies and here are some examples: in Thailand several dietary supplements containing heat-killed bacteria have been authorized by the Thai FDA, whereas the Chinese government has no official position, but industry and associations are working on quantification standards. The US has NDIs submitted for postbiotics (*e.g.*, fermentates of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and there are products with postbiotic ingredients on the market, while

Health Canada has no objection to the term postbiotics as long as it is presented with sufficient evidence in the non-traditional stream. Japan has no regulations specific to postbiotics but postbiotic ingredients have been used in foods and are possible under the current regulatory framework for food (FFC, Food with Functional Claim) provided they meet the requirements. In Europe, the use of the term 'postbiotic' is not regulated; postbiotic ingredients have to follow the regulations in place for foods and food supplements, or medicinal products, depending on their intended use. No regulations for postbiotic foods or food supplements currently exist in Brazil or Argentina. In Australia, the Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA) has allowed the inclusion of some postbiotic ingredients (inactivated microbes) in Listable Medicines.

Given the complexities of postbiotics, it is understandable that regulatory authorities face uncertainty regarding the appropriate steps to regulate these agents, which differ significantly from related products such as probiotics. Each type of postbiotic presents unique manufacturing requirements and testing challenges. These issues will be discussed below. With this in mind, regulatory authorities may need to divide approvals into smaller segments that better match the existing regulatory frameworks. Safety is paramount in all these considerations and will be addressed when discussing the manufacturing of postbiotic ingredients (paragraph 5.2).

4. The classification of postbiotic ingredients

The available scientific literature, although heterogeneous, suggests the classification of postbiotics into the following subcategories (Table 2 and Fig. 1):

- Complex non-viable microbial preparations (Subcategory CX): Bioactive ingredients consisting of unpurified culture medium containing microbial cells and/or cell fractions. A possible example includes microbial cells inactivated through thermal treatment within their culture medium.
- Intact non-viable microbial cells (Subcategory IC): Bioactive ingredients consisting of intentionally inactivated (non-viable) whole microbial cells, separated from the culture medium.
- Fragmented microbial cells (Subcategory FC): Bioactive ingredients consisting of intentionally fragmented microbial cells (*e.g.*, lysates or cell extracts), separated from the culture medium.

This subcategory includes a mixture of microbial cell components and includes cell wall extracts, membrane extracts, and intracellular molecules.

- Microbial metabolic products (Subcategory MM): Bioactive ingredients consisting of the metabolic products of microbial cells within their unpurified or partially purified culture medium (*e.g.*, spent culture medium). This subcategory includes secreted enzymes, capsule polymers such as exopolysaccharides (EPS), bacteriocins, reuterin, and other metabolites. Additionally, it may encompass products resulting from microbial biotransformation of exogenous molecules present in the culture medium (*e.g.*, equol from daidzin).

It should be noted that nature-identical synthetic components fall outside this scope, as a microbial origin is mandatory. Furthermore, purified molecules are also excluded from these subcategories as they can be referred to by their specific names.

Distinguishing between the aforementioned postbiotic subcategories requires a precise understanding of the manufacturing processes used to produce the agent. Key considerations include, but are not limited to: (i) whether the microbial strains have been intentionally inactivated, (ii) whether an individual compound has been purified, and (iii) the composition of the bulk ingredient or final product, as this directly impacts product classification. A decision tree outlining the assignment a 'biotic ingredient' to one of these postbiotic subcategories is presented in Fig. 1.

The ingredient classification does not automatically dictate the classification of the final product. A product containing ingredients from different subcategories is classified under the subcategory of the ingredient whose composition is least defined. For example, a product containing a cell wall extract from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (subcategory FC), blended with bovine milk pasteurized after fermentation with *Lactobacillus paracasei* (subcategory CX), would be classified under subcategory CX, provided that both the yeast cell wall extract and the fermented milk are bioactive.

Many of the above points pertain to commercially sensitive information, proprietary knowledge, or intellectual property; therefore, disclosure should be confined to regulatory applications or notifications rather than made publicly available. This distinction enables regulators to better assess the nuances between product ingredients and determine which claims may or may not be allowed depending on the level of substantiation provided.

The assignment of an ingredient according to the subdivision mentioned above may be modified primarily based on aspects related to product stability, manufacturing, and quality, or other aspects of product formulation and development. Such considerations will be addressed in subsequent sections of this document.

5. Manufacturing of postbiotic ingredients

5.1. General considerations

The industrial production of postbiotic ingredients begins with the cultivation of microbial biomass, similar to the industrial preparation of suitable-grade microbes such as probiotics or starter cultures. The components of the culture medium must be suitable for use in food and optimized for the growth of the target microorganism. Additionally, the microbiological purity of the target organism must be ensured, again not dissimilar to the industrial production of other food-grade microbes. Following fermentation, the culture medium with metabolites can be separated from the cells and used as a MM postbiotic subcategory. Alternatively, the entire product of the fermentation, including both inactivated cells and culture medium, can be used to produce a subcategory CX postbiotic ingredient. When the culture medium is separated from the cells, it can undergo further processing in various ways. **If specific components of the culture medium are purified or isolated through extensive downstream processing, they fall outside the scope of this paper.**

Although various inactivation techniques exist, they must be integrated into the production process. Depending on the inactivation method, it may be possible to separate fragments from the cell envelope and cytoplasm. Consequently, multiple approaches can be used to produce different types of postbiotics (Fig. 2). These ingredients have specific manufacturing and quality control requirements, which will be discussed in more detail below.

5.2. Starting material: safety considerations for postbiotic production

The absence of an established regulatory framework for postbiotics presents a formidable challenge in developing safety standards. Safety criteria may vary depending on the ingredient's nature, ranging from entire inactivated cells and their constituents to individual metabolites and cell components.

It is noteworthy that all postbiotics originate from live microbes and their parent strains. Therefore, part of the safety standards for postbiotics should logically align with those established for live microbes, as they serve as the initial starting material for postbiotic production. While global regulatory authorities universally recognize the importance of safety in relation to live microbes or probiotics, their methodologies and the studies used to assess microbial safety vary significantly ¹⁶.

The general safety of probiotics is assumed for specific microbial genera and species, such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and many lactic acid bacteria and bifidobacteria, that have an established history of safe use in various foods and dietary supplements worldwide. This acknowledgment is substantiated by numerous guidance documents, monographs, and publications ¹⁷. Furthermore, their presence as normal members in microbial ecosystems (microbiomes) associated with healthy humans further reinforces this assertion ¹⁶.

When dealing with a microbe lacking a documented history of safe usage and approval by a competent authority, a comprehensive safety evaluation becomes imperative. The microbe under scrutiny should be unequivocally taxonomically identified and characterized down to the strain level. For microbial strains intended for either product application or production purposes, a complete genome sequencing analysis is mandatory, as already foreseen in the applicable frameworks ¹⁸.

The introduction of microbial cells must not increase the existing reservoir of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes within the microbial population or facilitate their dissemination ^{16,19-21}. Although postbiotics do not multiply, their potential role in AMR gene transfer cannot be excluded ²². Genetic material carrying resistance genes may still be acquired by other microbes, though the actual risk remains unclear. Therefore, transferable antibiotic resistance remains a key safety consideration for those postbiotics in which the absence of genetic material derived from the progenitor microorganism has not been convincingly demonstrated.

A comprehensive safety evaluation must encompass the potential of a microorganism to express virulence or toxin genes that could potentially lead to disease or increase the risk of disease. For bacterial strains originating from species not featured in recognized positive lists, such as the Qualified Presumption of Safety (QPS) by EFSA or the “Inventory of microbial food cultures with safety demonstration in fermented food products” by FIL/IDF (Bulletin of the IDF N° 514/2022), or lacking any

established history of safe use, whole genome sequencing analysis (including both chromosomal and extrachromosomal genetic components such as plasmids) should be employed. This analysis aims to identify genes responsible for recognized virulence factors and/or the synthesis of known toxic metabolites. To achieve this, a comparison against specific, updated, and meticulously curated databases should be undertaken ^{16,19}. The detection of genes that encode virulence factors may necessitate further phenotypic testing, such as cytotoxicity tests of the obtained postbiotic ingredient ^{9,19,20}, or further demonstration of the lack of functionality of the gene present as a residue in the postbiotic.

To ensure the safety of postbiotics for human consumption, similar to probiotics, their production must adhere to Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) standards, universally recognized principles ²⁶⁻²⁸. Conformance to the appropriate GMP regulations ensures that operations and procedures are meticulously traceable, facilities and equipment meet the requisite specifications, materials are consistent with the intended product, and monitoring and control mechanisms for manufacturing processes are suitably aligned with risk considerations. Comprehensive systems should be established to guarantee the safety, quality, identity, purity, and potency of postbiotic ingredients in manufactured products and released by the producer ²⁶.

An essential component for ensuring product safety is the implementation of a risk management system to monitor chemical, allergenic, physical and biological/microbiological contaminants throughout the process. By integrating hazard analysis with GMPs, facilities can effectively identify operational prerequisites and critical control points (CCPs). These CCPs represent stages in the process where hazards must be managed to ensure safety and quality. Once identified, limits are established, closely monitored and corrective or preventive measures are implemented as needed. A well-functioning system integrates these interdependent requirements seamlessly, facilitated by diligent and comprehensive record-keeping.

Similar to other food-grade microbes, the production of postbiotics involves a range of ingredients, including various culture media constituents such as nitrogen sources, proteins, sources of carbon, vitamins, and minerals. These are essential for achieving optimal growth of the progenitor microbial biomasses. Additionally, additive ingredients may be included to standardize blends to achieve the

desired cell density. Each raw material must undergo thorough evaluation and quality control analysis prior to its use. This meticulous scrutiny ensures that the eventual postbiotic ingredient is not only fit for human consumption but also adheres to the SQuIPP criteria, which stands for “Safety, Quality, Identity, Potency, and Purity”.

Furthermore, the production process incorporates additional stages and in-process controls to confirm ingredient safety. For instance, risk management measures are implemented to reduce the likelihood of microbial contamination in the culture medium prior to inoculation. Additionally, testing for microbial contaminants and compliance with hygiene standards is conducted.

5.3. Microbial cell inactivation

Regardless of the definition used, the requirement is that postbiotics are non-viable due to intentional inactivation. For microbes, this may pose a challenge: when is a microbe non-viable or dead? Traditionally, microbial viability has been assessed through plate counting, where the formation of a colony indicates viability, and/or optical density, which measures the turbidity of a culture suspension. However, microbial cells can exist in various metabolic states that do not involve active replication. Besides culturing, other techniques can be used to determine the viability of microbial cells. These techniques commonly rely on cell membrane integrity, metabolic activity, or the presence/absence of mRNA²⁹. Ultimately, the appropriate technique for determining postbiotics depends on several factors, including sensitivity, applicability, and (further) regulatory acceptance. Assessing the absence of live cells and counting intact non-viable cells can be relatively straightforward. However, quantifying crude cell extracts and complex metabolic mixtures is more challenging. In analogy to botanical extracts, it may be necessary to standardize a specific component using analytic strategies such as chromatographic techniques or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). The units of enumeration and quantification (*e.g.*, colony forming units, active fluorescent units, cells, mg, relative activity) depend on the type of postbiotic agent and the techniques used.

After culturing, the spent culture liquid is commonly separated from the cells (Fig. 2). This is often done by continuous centrifugation, which does not kill microbes but reduces their number in the supernatant. Alternatively, microbes can be harvested by filtration; depending on the pore size used, the filtrate may

or may not be sterile ³⁰. These separation techniques isolate most of the two fractions, but not all. As indicated above, varying amounts of microbes may be present in the spent culture liquid. Similarly, varying amounts of spent culture liquid may be present in the retentate (i.e., the microbes' fraction) ³¹. The separated spent culture liquid (postbiotic subcategory MM) can undergo further downstream processing using specialized techniques for the isolation of specific metabolites. For the purpose of this article, molecules and cell components which are purified or isolated through extensive downstream processing are considered out of scope. However, separating microbes and spent culture liquid may not always be necessary, since also the whole fermentation broth can be used for the preparation of a postbiotic (subcategory CX).

The food and pharmaceutical industry have long implemented techniques to inactivate microbes, with heat being the most used method. Other techniques, such as UV, ionizing radiation, high pressure, and shear forces, can also be used ³², but they may require substantial investments or be challenging to implement in the production process.

To produce postbiotics, high temperature appears to be the most feasible approach to inactivate microbes, commonly done through pasteurization or sterilization ³³. While these processes are well-known in the food industry, the specific application of heat treatments can significantly impact the properties of the final ingredient. Heat treatments, in particular, might promote Maillard reactions and caramelization, and may lead to protein denaturation, potentially altering the surface properties of microbial cells and affecting crucial aspects such as adhesion and immunomodulatory properties. In this context, the use of gamma radiation, occasionally employed to enhance safety and extend the shelf life of foods/ingredients, appears to be a promising tool for industrially preparing biomasses of microbial cells that have lost the ability to replicate while preserving the structural integrity of cells ³⁴. However, the observation that gamma irradiation preserves membrane integrity and metabolic activity ³⁴ may raise questions about whether such non-replicating cells can be properly considered dead. In addition, the use of gamma radiation on food is strictly regulated, with specific requirements for labelling in some regulatory regions (*e.g.*, the Radura symbol in USA).

The reproducibility and controllability of the process and product require that nothing is left to chance. Scaling up can also significantly impact the resulting preparation. Thus, multiple technical decisions will

shape the reproducibility and controllability of a postbiotic, especially if production occurs at multiple sites. A poorly stored batch of probiotics in a warehouse cannot qualify as a postbiotic, as it is not intentionally inactivated. For such a product, the process conditions are undefined and uncontrolled, making reproducibility unlikely. Conversely, a product containing viable microbial cells stored under defined and controlled conditions intended to inactivate the live microbes for a prolonged period could qualify as a postbiotic, provided the process is verifiably reproducible and resulting microbes are rendered inactive.

The production process is, therefore, central to the consistent and responsible manufacturing of postbiotic agents. This may provide opportunities for patent protection, although enforcement may be challenging, or a manufacturer may opt to keep the process a trade secret. In both cases, protecting a carefully developed production process offers a way to valorize the investment made in its development.

Following the intentional inactivation or killing of the microbe, additional downstream processing can be performed using standard biotech industry techniques.

5.4. Qualification: enumeration and quantification techniques

While the idea of postbiotic ingredients is relatively new, inactivated microbial cells and their components, metabolites and exogenous substances generated through microbial fermentation, such as vitamins and conjugated linoleic acid, have been known and studied for a considerable period. Techniques for detecting and measuring these substances have been refined and improved over time. Moreover, there are ongoing efforts to devise innovative methods that promise even greater precision and speed in testing. However, when designing such methods, it is crucial to validate them in the context of the matrix into which postbiotics are incorporated. It could be possible that a combination of techniques is required for proper quantification.

Subcategory CX

Subcategory CX agents encompass complex mixtures of multiple ingredients found in the culture broth, with the presence of microbial cells and/or microbial cell components. Quantification based on the measurement of weight or volume is an acceptable method so long as they are validated and fit for

purpose, such as quantification of cells microscopically after staining with fluorescent dyes. However, if a specific active compound within the complex mixture has clinically proven beneficial physiological effects for consumers, it becomes advantageous to identify and quantify it, allowing it to serve as the efficacy and standardization marker for the entire mixture. This is similar to standardizations used for some plant extracts. Chromatographic methods such as gas and liquid chromatography (GC and LC) are interesting methods to quantify organic acids in fermented products³⁵, while NMR-based metabolomics is suitable for identification and quantification of metabolites, SCFAs and more in complex mixtures during the development of a product, and for characterization purposes^{35,36}. Considering the nature of the matrix, it is more than likely that the quantification method for the compound will require adaptation and/or optimization and validation. The most relevant aspect of this subcategory is to build data sets that demonstrate that the postbiotic ingredient can be manufactured in a repeatable way and that specifications should be designed to demonstrate that.

Subcategory FC

This subcategory includes components that make up the structure of microbial cells separated from the culture medium but does not include significant amount of inactivated cells. DNA-based methods are suitable for quantifying cell lysate where DNA is expected to be present in amounts equivalent to the original cells, without losses during processing. These methods include Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) based techniques³⁷, which, with appropriate primer design, can enable discrimination down to the subspecific level; both real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR) and digital chip-based or droplet PCR (cdPCR or ddPCR) can be used for identification and quantification of DNA. Both methods can identify specific targets using species or strain-specific primers along with fluorescent dyes or probes to amplify and identify specific genomic regions^{38,39}. Biomass concentration is an alternative quantification option, as it can be standardized to a specific concentration^{40,41}. However, this method lacks specificity. In this case, the cell lysate would be reported in terms of mg per dose or per unit of weight/volume of the ingredient. Another option would be quantification by input where the number of cells is standardized after fermentation and then inactivated. Additionally, a suitable approach for cell lysates is the quantification of a specific cell component that serves as a marker, such as cell membrane- or wall-

associated proteins ^{40,42}. This marker is then quantified using an appropriate analytical method and reported accordingly.

Subcategory IC

This subcategory primarily consists of inactivated whole cells that have been separated from their culture medium and metabolites. Several validated methods are available and currently employed in the market to distinguish between live from dead cells. Culture-independent methods are better adapted to determine the whole cell count and differentiate between dead and live cells. Depending on the application, sterility of the postbiotic ingredient may not be required, and an acceptable upper level of residual live microbes would need to be determined – these thresholds can vary by regulatory region. In this perspective, it is important to note that probiotic products also contain dead microbes ⁴³.

Flow cytometry is a technology that provides rapid multi-parametric analysis of single cells in suspension, utilizing reagents such as fluorescent proteins, fluorescent dyes and fluorescently conjugated antibodies to identify cell traits like viability, size, and granularity through light scatter and fluorescence measurements ⁴⁴. In 2015, ISO published an international standard for the enumeration of lactic acid bacteria by flow cytometry (ISO 19344 IDF 232). The method offers three different protocols to enumerate live, dead, damaged and total cell count ^{37,45,46}. Strain identification and enumeration in a multi-strain blend can be achieved with the use of strain-specific antibodies, though this is technically quite challenging ⁴⁷. Also, PCR-based methods are suitable culture-independent methods to identify and enumerate inactivated cells ^{38,39}. Notably, the use of viability dyes in PCR, such as propidium monoazide (PMA), allows for the enumeration of dead microbial cells ⁴⁸. The cells are then reported as inactivated cells per unit of weight/volume or dose.

Such indirect methods are currently mainly used to assess microbial viability in probiotic or other microbial preparations, but since they can discriminate dead from live cells, they are also reasonably adequate for enumerating inactivated cells.

Subcategory MM

This subcategory includes complex mixtures of compounds originating from microbial metabolism, such as SCFAs, vitamins, bacteriocins, or molecules resulting from microbial biotransformation of exogenous

molecules (*e.g.*, plant polyphenols). Compounds originating from microbial metabolism in subcategory MM, such as SCFAs, vitamins, and bacteriocins, can be identified and quantified using established techniques like GC-MS, LC-MS, or NMR spectroscopy, as already mentioned for subcategory CX, with adaptations as needed for complex samples.

5.5. Shelf life and stability

One of the driving forces behind the interest in postbiotic agents is their perceived greater stability compared to probiotics. This stability generally enables their potential inclusion in matrices that are hostile to live microorganisms, in products stored under adverse conditions for live microorganisms, and in food products that could be altered by the addition of live microbial cells ^{1,2,8}. However, is this perception accurate? As a reference, we can consider preserved and/or processed or ultra-processed foods. Although such foods are typically sterile, they generally have a 'best before' date. This is not necessarily because the food spoils: it is often due to changes in their characteristics over time, including the nutritional value. For instance, some vitamins are unstable, fats may hydrolyze, and oxidation can occur, among other factors. Enzymatic and non-enzymatic reactions, as well as oxidation, will influence the stability of a postbiotic ingredient. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that a postbiotic ingredient will not have an indefinite shelf life ⁹, although it will likely be longer than that of its corresponding probiotic. Proper stability studies must be conducted for each postbiotic ingredient.

The carrier matrix plays a significant role in stability. The components in the matrix can affect the characteristics and functionality of the postbiotic agents, especially considering components like emulsifiers and detergents. Protective packaging, important for probiotics as a barrier to moisture and oxygen, may therefore also remain relevant for postbiotic ingredients.

To assess shelf life, stability testing in the realm of postbiotics is essential for evaluating how their quality evolves over time under different environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and light exposure. Organizations, such as the International Council for Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH), provide comprehensive guidelines on stability testing to ensure that products meet quality standards over shelf life. These tests are critical for determining the optimal packaging materials and methods to preserve finished product attributes, nutritional integrity,

and safety during storage and transport. By rigorously analyzing these factors, manufacturers can provide precise recommendations to ensure that these products maintain their quality throughout their intended shelf life as required by Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP, ^{49,50}), meeting regulatory requirements and consumer expectations reliably.

6. A word on beneficial physiological effects

How the efficacy of an ingredient (i.e., the beneficial physiological effect for a consumer) is advertised or labeled on product packaging is subject to each regulatory body's existing rules and frameworks. Laws and guidelines for postbiotic ingredients can fall under these same framework structures. This publication deliberately does not address efficacy; its aim is to define, describe, and reconcile concepts within the postbiotic category so that they are understood by all stakeholders. The efficacy from a live probiotic should not be carried over to an inactivated postbiotic that originates from that same strain or a blend of strains. Notwithstanding, it should be stressed once again that if a candidate postbiotic does not provide a demonstrable beneficial physiological effect, it cannot be classified as a postbiotic.

The need for scientific evidence to prove efficacy should align with standard practice, with randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled studies remaining the gold standard for evidence-based claims. However, many regulatory authorities allow "active" ingredients in consumer products without requiring efficacy data, provided that the material is labeled appropriately. This approach does not need to change specifically for postbiotic agents.

Due to the limited clinical trial evidence available for postbiotics, it is challenging to determine whether they offer more, fewer, or different beneficial physiological effects compared to their live progenitors. Nonetheless, as long as postbiotics demonstrate a positive effect, this comparison may be irrelevant.

Postbiotics and probiotics are likely to complement rather than replace each other, serving distinct purposes in different applications. Advances in technology may further expand the potential of this ingredient category, but their full impact will only become clear over time. Postbiotics offer both different options and practical advantages and disadvantages compared to their live counterparts. The choice between postbiotics and probiotics will depend on factors such as efficacy, mechanism of action,

shared confidentially with regulatory authorities and protected as proprietary information. This approach allows regulatory authorities to gain the necessary insights into ingredient under evaluation while providing consumers with sufficient information to understand the product. Additionally, any standardized or measured components must be clearly quantified and presented in a manner comprehensible to consumers.

8. Nomenclature and labelling

All active ingredients in a product must appear on the label, and this applies to products containing postbiotic ingredients as well. Therefore, each agent must have a suitable name for this purpose. It is not enough to use an umbrella term like “postbiotic”, “paraprobiotic”, or “metabolite” to identify an ingredient, as this does not provide sufficient detail about what is included in a product. The nomenclature of these agents must be clearly defined. Consumers need to be able to discern for themselves what they are consuming without professional guidance or explanation. Just as live progenitors have a specific genus, (sub-) species, and strain specified, accurately describing the exact material being added to a product is critical and we must articulate the same for all varieties of postbiotics.

- Subcategories IC and FC agents are relatively uncomplicated. They are cellular in nature, and therefore, the genus, species and strain of the organism based on the most up-to-date taxonomic classification should be used, with an additional indication of “inactivated” or a similar term if it is a whole cell, or terms such as “lysate” for parts of a cell.
- Subcategories CX and MM ingredients include more complex agents as they involve mixtures of multiple ingredients and components that are not completely defined. Typical examples for subcategory CX are represented by bovine milk fermented by *L. paracasei*, pasteurized and lyophilized, while typical examples for subcategory MM are represented by lyophilized cell-free spent culture medium containing EPS. A simple terminology of genus, species and strain, and the word “ferment” with the mention of the substance of interest (*e.g.*, EPS) may suffice, provided the relevant regulatory agency has assessed the ingredient.

The final label on a finished product reflects its formulation, manufacturing process, and quality standards. Regulatory authorities are responsible for establishing labeling laws for the products under

their governance. Each subcategory of finished product already has basic labeling guidelines set by local regulatory authorities, which generally do not need to change to accommodate additional ingredients from various categories. Standard labeling requirements should include the product's expiration date, storage conditions, and serving size or dose per day, regardless of the subcategory of the postbiotic agent included.

Nomenclature, as previously discussed, must be expressed as required and will be specific to the subcategory of the postbiotic agent used. Additionally, the label must indicate the quantity of the postbiotic agent, expressed in appropriate units of measurement reflective of the subcategory of postbiotic used. This is more complex than merely indicating weight and it is further detailed in section “5.4. Qualification: enumeration and quantification techniques.” The quantity of the postbiotic agent is also tied to clinical studies for the product's effects. Consumers need to clearly identify if a product contains an amount per dose or serving that has demonstrated beneficial physiological effects. Labels should be clear enough for non-expert consumers to easily understand this information without professional guidance, as previously discussed under efficacy.

In conclusion, similar to the recommendations for probiotic foods and supplements (FAO/WHO, 2002; FAO/WHO and Codex, 2019), in addition to the general standard for labelling of prepackaged foods, the labels of postbiotic-containing products should adhere to the following specific provisions:

- Name of the microbe(s) (genus, species and strain) from which the postbiotic ingredient is derived;
- Type of postbiotic
- The quantity of the postbiotic ingredient in the appropriate unit; guaranteed at end of shelf life.
- Serving size or dose;
- Proper storage conditions;
- Expiry date;
- Corporate contact details for consumer information.

It is evident that all aspects discussed in this article are interconnected with the final product labeling and are crucial for ensuring adequate consumer communication and understanding of the products and ingredients they are consuming.

10. Final remarks and conclusions

To date, there is no academic, commercial, regulatory, or legal consensus as to what term(s) best represents which postbiotic(s) and how the multiple existing definitions (shown in Table 1) should be harmonized, interpreted and applied. This has resulted in substantial complexity and confusion for the postbiotic industry with wide-ranging impacts and opportunities for misuse. From the marketing and communication side, the confusion of terms and invention of new ones for products launched on the market have both converged and diverged the basic historical concepts of postbiotics

Non-profit associations have played a pivotal role in shaping the strategic directions of their industries and, historically, have had the power to influence an industry's reputation significantly. Representing industries and providing guidance and clarity, such as serving as nongovernmental observers at organizations like Codex Alimentarius and ISO, is a fundamental aspect of their mission. A notable example is the International Probiotics Association, established in 1999 to support the probiotic industry. Leveraging the extensive knowledge and experience in the probiotic industry can pave the way for better adaptation to evolving challenges for postbiotics.

The stewardship of a non-profit association for postbiotics is essential and will be highly beneficial for representing, advocating and providing clarity, while simultaneously advancing the science, research, and frameworks needed for this category. Currently, there is a lack of clear guidance from regulatory authorities, and insufficient bilateral communication and education to promote true clarity in the field. A dedicated association, like IPA, will play a pivotal role in stewarding key aspects, ensuring credibility and transparency, and helping to build the category based on the following strategic pillars: advocacy and regulatory affairs, championing quality standards and scientific research and development, category stewardship, and fostering stakeholder interactions.

The most fundamental tipping point is the harmonization of the concepts discussed in this manuscript towards a true consensus on definition and interpretation of the word "postbiotic". This will ensure consistency and facilitate communication between researchers, industry, regulators, consumers, and authorities. Establishing clarity in the definitions and criteria will lay foundation for guidance in the category. Appropriate 'branding' of terms associated with the "postbiotic" category, in addition to aligning definitions, will be essential for all stakeholders. The use of the term "postbiotic" is already

widespread; however, without further alignment on its meaning and appropriate nomenclature, the highly heterogeneous postbiotic category runs the risk of remaining a “marketing gimmick”.

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Tables

Table 1. Evolution of terms and concepts related to postbiotics. The list is not exhaustive and starts with the earliest identified uses of terms and concepts related to postbiotics, then traces their evolution in academic literature. Definitions of the term 'postbiotic' appear in blue text, whereas the other terms appear in black text.

Year	Term	Summary of the context behind the term	Reference
1877	Tyndallized	process of inactivating microbes	Tyndall, ⁵³
1970s	Lysates	microbes inactivated by various methods	-
2009	Postbiotics	metabolites (by-products of probiotic cultures)	Johannsen & Prescott, ⁵
2010	Probiotaceuticals	metabolites (secreted probiotic factors)	Howarth, ⁵⁴
2011	Paraprobiotics	microbial cells (inactivated microbial cells, intact or broken, or crude extracts)	Taverniti & Guglielmetti, ¹¹
2012	Postbiotics	metabolites (metabolic products of probiotics)	Tsilingiri et al., ⁶
2013	Postbiotics	metabolites (probiotic-produced, soluble factors)	Tsilingiri & Rescigno ⁷
	Postbiotics	metabolites (nonviable products or metabolic byproducts of probiotics)	Patel & Denning, ⁵⁵
	Metabiotic	structural components of probiotics, their metabolites, signaling molecules	Shenderov, ¹⁴
2017	Parapsychobiotics	a type of paraprobiotic that has specific effects on stress and sleep quality	Nishida, ⁵⁶
2017	proteobiotics	metabolites of probiotics	Nordeste, ⁵⁷
2018	Postbiotics	metabolites and/or cell-wall components from probiotics	Aguilar-Toala et al., ⁵⁸
	Postbiotics	metabolites (bioactive compounds generated during fermentation)	Wegh et al., ⁵⁹
	Postbiotics	microbial metabolites	Martin & Langella, ⁶⁰
2019	Postbiotics	metabolites (compounds produced by microbes, released from food components or microbial constituents, including non-viable cells)	Collado et al., ⁶¹
	Postbiotics	metabolites (bacterial products or metabolic byproducts from probiotics)	Johnson et al., ⁶²
	Postbiotics	metabolites (soluble secreted factors and cell-free supernatant)	Foo et al., ⁶³
2020	Postbiotics	metabolites (any substance released or produced by microbial metabolism)	Kiewicz et al., ¹⁰
	Bioactive compounds	bioactive compounds produced by probiotic bacteria	Chugh & Kamal-Eldin, ⁶⁴
	Postbiotics	metabolites (healthful metabolites of probiotics)	Zendeboodi et al., ⁶⁵
	Ghost probiotic	microbial cells (dead/nonviable cell, intact or ruptured)	Zendeboodi et al., ⁶⁵
	Postbiotics	metabolites (complex mixture of metabolic products secreted by probiotics)	Nataraj et al., ⁶⁶
	Fermentate	microbial cells (active or inactive) and metabolites	Mathur et al., ⁶⁷
	Paraprobiotics	microbial cells (Inactivated cells, intact or ruptured, or crude extracts of probiotics)	Nataraj et al., ⁶⁶
2021	Paraprobiotics	microbial cells (inactivated/non-viable microbial cells)	Siciliano et al., ³³
	Postbiotics	microbial cells with or without metabolites	Salminen et al., ⁸
	Postbiotics	metabolites (soluble factors produced by probiotics)	Peluzio et al., ¹²
2023	Postbiotics	metabolites (beneficial molecules produced by probiotic bacteria)	Rafique et al., ¹³

Table 2. Summary of the main features characterizing the proposed subcategories of postbiotics.

Subcategory	Description	Specification	Examples	Suggested strategy for quantification/enumeration	Regulatory considerations in approval process
CX (Complex non-viable microbial preparations)	Bioactive ingredients consisting of unpurified culture medium containing intentionally inactivated (non-viable) microbial cells and/or cell fractions.	Any mixture of different postbiotics results into this subcategory.	Bovine milk fermented by <i>Lactocaseibacillus paracasei</i> , pasteurized and lyophilized.	Depending on the presence of intact cells or cell fractions (broken cells), a combination of the methods reported below for the other subcategories can be applied.	Progenitor approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, or final ingredient approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations (or probiotic or starter culture), ability to directly measure and quantify amounts, inactivation step and verification, purification process, demonstration of effect and dose.
Ic (Intact non-viable microbial cells)	Bioactive ingredients consisting of intentionally inactivated (non-viable) whole microbial cells, separated from the culture medium.	Most cells must remain intact, meaning they should not be broken. Intact non-viable cells are defined here as those that retain recognizable morphology when observed under a phase-contrast light microscope.	Pasteurized and freeze-dried biomass of <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i> .	Agar plate count before cell inactivation; flow cytometry; qPCR.	Progenitor approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, or final ingredient approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations (or probiotic or starter culture), ability to measure and quantify amounts, inactivation step and verification, demonstration of effect and dose.
FC (Fragmented microbial cells)	Bioactive ingredients consisting of intentionally fragmented microbial cells, separated from the culture medium.	This subcategory includes cell lysates or cell extracts (e.g. cell wall extracts, membrane extracts, and intracellular molecules).	Crude extracts of <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> cells.	It can be standardized through the quantification of a specific cell component that can act as a marker (e.g., cell membrane- or wall-associated proteins). Standardization of cell fragmentation is also required.	Progenitor approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, or final ingredient approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, ability to directly measure and quantify amounts, inactivation step and verification, purification process, demonstration of effect and dose.
MM (Microbial metabolic products)	Bioactive ingredients consisting of metabolic products of microbial cells within their unpurified or partially purified culture medium	This subcategory includes secreted metabolites (e.g., organic acids, enzymes, capsule polymers) and products derived from microbial biotransformation of exogenous molecules (e.g. equol from daidzin). Any mixture of different postbiotics results into this subcategory.	Lyophilized cell-free spent culture medium containing EPS.	It can be standardized using a reference compound present within it.	Progenitor approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, or final ingredient approved or recognized as safe per applicable regulations, ability to directly measure and quantify at least a bioactive component, inactivation step and verification, purification process, demonstration of effect and dose.

Figures

Fig. 1. Proposed decision tree for the classification of postbiotics (non-viable agents of microbial origin conferring a beneficial physiological effect) as foods and dietary supplements.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the production process for various postbiotic ingredients. CX, FC, IC, and MM refer to the postbiotic subcategories as described in Table 1 and Fig. 1. Note that combinations of these products are also possible, resulting in an ingredient classified under the CX subcategory.

